

Session Report: Identifying the critical software underpinning UKRI DRI

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Overview

This workshop presented the findings of recent studies by the Software Sustainability Institute, before working with participants to identify and discuss the software that they consider to be critical to the operation of the DRI that they use or operate.

The aims of the workshop were to:

- Identify widely used pieces of software that are considered “critical components” of DRI
- Categorise the risks, and identify any which would benefit from collective mitigation
- Recommend actions that could feed into strategy and policy for DRIs and the UKRI DRI programme

Approximately 20 people participated in-person at the 2025 UKRI DRI Congress held in Leeds, representing a variety of roles (infrastructure providers, funders, researchers, research technical professionals) and research council remits. A combination of presentations, interactive polling and group discussions were utilised as part of the session.

Understanding Critical Software for UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure

Ben Thomas gave a summary of the study that he led on the critical software for UKRI DRI. He presented the methodology, which used a combination of desk research, interviews and focus groups, resulting in definitions and recommendations.

Based on the input from participants in the study, what constituted “Critical Software” was defined as:

- There being no viable alternative
 - Discussed in relation to the cost or effort required to switch. Concerns here were tied to the resources that infrastructures had to address software challenges.
- The negative consequences of software no longer working.
 - This was discussed as affecting either the whole or part of the software stack, the severity of the failure, being an imminent consequence or at sometime in the future, and in relation to how much each person is affected vs. how many people are affected.

The perceived risks to software included:

- Limited or no maintenance from developers or communities
- A lack of internal skilled staff to support/maintain software
- Licensing changes
- Cost of support from commercial providers
- Changes in governance
- Security failures
- Incorrect/immature code

As well as cross-cutting themes such as Funding & lack of risk assessment/audit

The full report can be found at:

Thomas, B., Chue Hong, N., & Hettrick, S. (2025). Understanding Critical Software for UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16848311>

Perceptions of risk

Participants at the session were asked a series of questions about how they perceived risks relating to software, and how this interacted with the definitions of critical software.

Which of these risks to software do you see most often in your job? (Choose your top three)

Multiple Choice Poll 18 votes 18 participants

Which of these risks to software do you think will have become more important to assess in 3-5 years time? (Choose your top three)

Multiple Choice Poll 16 votes 16 participants

slido

Lack of maintenance, and shortage of skilled staff were seen as major risks both in the short and medium-term, with security failures being seen as a key risk that would become more important to mitigate in the future.

Potential additional risks to be considered, that were suggested by participants included:

- Strategic shifts
 - Government drive towards certain areas of scientific software causing skilled staff to train towards “where the money is” meaning there isn’t the skilled staff in the software areas outside of these
 - More emphasis on building web tools to make research available and security implications of this
 - Lack of recognition in the value of research codes based on current bias in research funding
- Impact of Artificial Intelligence
 - Loss of IP due to uncontrolled use of AI in code development
 - Becoming more AI generated
- Interaction between research and software
 - Not understanding the basic science underlying the code
 - Limiting research because the software paradigms haven’t kept up
- Dealing with legacy code
 - Legacy code in unexpected places
 - Interdependencies
 - Too much of it? Compounding legacy
 - Abandoned dependencies
 - Continued use of a product/package when the researcher should using something else
- Increasingly complex software, harder for users to understand / people to maintain.
- Lack of obvious shared approaches

Mitigating risks

Participants were then asked to split into groups to consider potential risks and mitigations.

There were four groups, covering the following categories of risk:

- Group 1 - Maintenance
- Group 2 - Security & Immature Code
- Group 3 - Licensing and Governance
- Group 4 - Cost of Support

Each group was asked to:

- Discuss and identify the types of software that might be most exposed to that risk
- Discuss and recommend potential mitigations and solutions for that risk

They were then asked to report back:

- One example of a type of software / piece of software exemplifying that risk
- Top three recommendations for mitigation (where, if possible, they were asked to choose one recommendation which is a “quick win” and one which is a longer, complex solution to implement)

Group 1 - Maintenance

Software dependencies

- 1) Prioritise good code hygiene (e.g. using tools like Dependabot)
- 2) Encourage use of Software Bill of Materials
- 3) Move to promoting programming languages that are better at handling dependencies (e.g. Rust)

Group 2 - Security & Immature Code

Software used on Trusted Research Environments

- 1) Encourage users to use software versions supplied by TRE infrastructure providers, rather than bringing their own
- 2) Provide better training for users on the risks related to security
- 3) Restrictions placed on software for security reasons should be framed as enablers

Group 3 - Licensing and Governance

VMWare raising it's annual licensing prices by 10x

- 1) Pooling effort for customising / supporting open source alternatives
- 2) Support for helping DRI to price their software (what's the market value of the tools we produce?)
- 3) Audits for software to feed into risk registers
 - a) Regular survey across institutions on top three concerns?
 - b) Sharing “early warning / red flags” e.g. VC buy out of software vendor

Group 4 - Cost of Support

KML Visualizer

- 1) Communicate the cost of software maintenance
- 2) More software maintenance grants
- 3) Don't underestimate costs on grants

There were some cross-cutting ideas that also came out:

- The idea of encouraging “good code hygiene” was seen to be very important, and fed into the mitigations from both Group 1 and Group 2. Software Bill of Materials were seen as something that could help enable this
- Anonymous sharing and publishing of certain data that are often hard to find examples of, such as cost of support, how to price the value of software, number of users, early warning flags etc, would make it easier for the community to make better decisions

What critical software is at risk?

Finally, participants were asked to suggest software that should be considered critical, and explain the risks that were driving this.

Suggestions included:

- Not sure if at risk, but **research data repository systems** (being bought by commercial and lock-ins)
- **Tidyverse** - the R data processing packages. Risks include fragmentation and bloat
- **Kubernetes** - skills competition with banks etc
- **The Funding Service** - needs to be fit for use
- **lustre** - skills, expertise (lack of)
- **CEPH** - skills, finance
- Easy to use software for **managing Python and Python packages** (risk with changes in Anaconda licence).
- **Workflow management packages** (e.g. Nextflow). Risks include fragmentation and security implications
- **Openstack**
- **Online Git hosting**. Big reliance on GitHub with few alternatives.
- Mature **Software Development Environments** for multiple vendor environments i.e., AMD vs CUDA / NVIDIA
- **AAAI integration** (will it ever be comprehensive?) Risk of never being developed or not comprehensive across the whole research landscape
- All the **national asset research data** in locked out of access software
- **Package management (singularity/apptainer)** risk is fragmentation

Final Thoughts

A number of common themes ran through this workshop session. One was that the assessment of an infrastructure's use of software, as a precursor to understanding what software is critical and what risks need to be mitigated, is often competing for resources that could be used for other aspects of the infrastructure. Having a structured way to enable this conversation is important, and the Digital Preservation Coalition's Rapid Assessment Model was given as an example of how this has been addressed in other domains. The SSI will investigate how this can be taken forward in follow-on work around software audit and assessment. The second was around understanding and sharing what the community perceives as the warning signs which indicate an underlying risk to the software. A third was around having trusted parties who could aggregate and share data anonymously that would help the community benchmark against different aspects of supporting critical software. These latter two which have the potential to be taken forward by organisations like the SSI, Jisc and UKRI.

Finally, it is clear that a lot of software is seen as critical in some way to different areas of research, and a challenge is understanding how to properly support it. This can only happen through a cultural shift that values investment in infrastructure maintenance and further discussion is needed about the way that this value can be recognised in a way that will lead to changes in funding models.